

Open Science “Dynamic Convergence” Workshop

*Final report prepared by the Open Research Community
Accelerator (ORCA)*

October 2024

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The Open Research Community Accelerator ([ORCA](#)), in collaboration with CERN and UNESCO and with the participation of NASA and the National Science Foundation, organized the “Dynamic Convergence” Workshop on Open Science, held on September 18–19, 2024, in Washington, DC.

This international event brought together a diverse range of participants, including researchers, policymakers, and funders, with the aim of advancing global collaboration to make science more accessible, inclusive, and impactful. Generous funding from the Gordon and Betty Moore Foundation[1], the Templeton World Charity Foundation[2], the Chan Zuckerberg Initiative[3], NASA[4], and the National Science Foundation[5] supported the workshop.

The primary objectives of the workshop were to highlight significant open science initiatives, foster new collaboration opportunities, explore shared agendas with parallel efforts like community engagement and citizen science, and identify practical steps to accelerate the global adoption of open science practices.

Participants were selected through both invitations and an open call, which ensured a diverse group from different geographies, career stages, and disciplines. Financial support allowed early-career researchers and international attendees to participate, broadening the perspectives shared at the event. Post-meeting feedback indicated that bringing new perspectives into the open science discussion helped widen participants’ networks specifically and their sense of community more generally.

The program was designed around three major themes: engagement, coordination, and acceleration. The workshop featured panel discussions, lightning talks, breakout sessions, and a hackathon, with participants engaging in in-depth conversations on these themes. The workshop outcomes highlighted several key areas for action.

[1] GRANT ID: [GBMF12347.01](#)

[2] GRANT ID: [TWCF-2024-33356](#)

[3] GRANT ID PENDING

[4] NASA GRANT ID: [80NSSC24K1733](#)

[5] NSF GRANT ID: [2437807](#)

During the workshop, a number of challenges and opportunities were identified. A recurrent theme was the misalignment of researcher incentives with the goals of open science, as traditional metrics still dominate academic reward structures despite the limited insights they provide.

Participants expressed an interest in addressing tenure culture and institutional inertia, emphasizing the need to develop new evaluation systems to better value open science activities. Additionally, there was consensus on the need for more robust methods to assess both societal and academic impacts of open science, with suggestions to develop frameworks that capture diverse forms of impact across various domains such as society, science, economy, and governance.

Lastly, a strong call emerged for improved coordination and convening efforts in open science, including sharing resources, fostering collaboration, and creating decentralized networks of practice to enhance communication and agency. The event concluded with participants identifying several possible activities to operationalize these themes, which were further validated via a post-meeting exit survey (see Key Next Steps section immediate following).

Plans are in place for ongoing collaboration and follow-up to ensure that the momentum generated at the workshop leads to meaningful and sustained progress in advancing open science globally.

KEY NEXT STEPS

Among the myriad workstreams surfaced over the multi-day discussion (detailed in the Workshop Execution section below), ORCA and the co-organizers are committed to actively stewarding the following workstreams:

INCENTIVES

Continuing to seek concrete ways to adapt credit and reward structures to fully recognize a range of open science activities

COALITION BUILDING

Identifying practical ways to expand what are considered to be the boundaries of open science and nurture a broad coalition.

MONITORING, EVALUATION & LEARNING

Designing a usable framework for funders and agencies to evaluate the impact of their open science policies.

COALITION BUILDING

Developing an open science champions program to build bridges across communities and disciplines, including ones that may not see themselves in open science.

INFORMATION SHARING

Establishing organic methods for open science community members to engage with each other, encompassing both online space and, potentially, an annual open science convening.

In these efforts, workshop organizers and participants are keen to collaborate with existing efforts in flight, amplifying and accelerating these wherever possible.

Noting that these are not the only potential workstreams that were surfaced at the meeting, and acknowledging that ORCA and the co-organizers are not the locus through which all activities should flow, we are also committed to assisting interested parties explore the following activities:

- Leveraging researchers' power as reviewers to change journal policies and procedures.
- Creating better transparency into institutional tenure and promotion policies and finding ways to encourage approaches that incorporate open science.
- Piloting an open source software development for better research evaluation processes, with international partners.
- Conceptualizing personas so that open science training can be more readily adapted to serve a wider array of communities.
- Localizing existing open science tools and information to reach beyond English/western audiences.
- Developing a typology of impact, with an emphasis on creating more efficient ways for open science practitioners to understand and articulate the qualitative impact of their activities.
- Building a “drag-and-drop my dataset” into an AI tool to determine the best place to deposit data, suggest other datasets similar to yours and potentially run a FAIR check.

For these activities, ORCA and the co-organizers can provide initial visibility, identify networking opportunities, and amplify the outputs of any community-led groups that emerge from these initial discussions.

In an effort to further broaden this circle and include a wide range of perspectives, the call is open to join any of the above workstreams by contacting Julieta Arancio at julieta@orcaopen.org

BACKGROUND

The Open Research Community Accelerator (ORCA), in collaboration with CERN and UNESCO and with the participation of NASA and the National Science Foundation, secured funding to host an Open Science “Dynamic Convergence” Workshop, September 18–19, 2024, in Washington, DC. The event was designed to accommodate an international roster of researchers, policymakers, funders, and others working together to make science more accessible, engaging, and actionable.

Among the key goals of the meeting: (1) highlighting impactful open science activities, (2) exploring collaboration opportunities, and (3) identifying practical ways to speed up the global adoption of open science. The workshop was made possible by generous support from the Gordon and Betty Moore Foundation, the Templeton World Charity Foundation, the Chan Zuckerberg Initiative, NASA, and the National Science Foundation.

A range of highly visible and impactful activities– including the US Office of Science and Technology Policy’s “Ensuring Free, Immediate, and Equitable Access to Federally Funded Research” [memorandum](#), UNESCO’s [Recommendation on Open Science](#), and the CERN/NASA “Accelerating the Adoption of Open Science” [Summit](#)– as well as actions taken by governments around the world (e.g., [Ireland](#), [Colombia](#), [Spain](#), and [France](#)) made the timing opportune for a “taking stock” meeting.

The meeting organizers shared a particular interest in convening an inclusive mix of participants spanning geographies, career stages, and disciplines, in order to better understand the range of opportunities and challenges across the open science community.

WORKSHOP DESIGN

Participant recruitment

To ensure that the workshop was populated by the aforementioned inclusive mix of participants, attendee recruitment was organized in two different stages: by invitation from the convening organizations, and via an open call for applications.

Across both streams, selection was guided by three key considerations:

1. Are the prospective participants actively advancing open, equitable, inclusive, and engaging practices and principles?
2. To what extent can the prospective participants uniquely sharpen our shared understanding of the open science landscape?
3. Are the prospective participants able to share experiences that could help inform the work of other participants, and are they likely to benefit from reciprocal sharing by others?

The open call received 146 responses. All applications were reviewed by at least two members of the organizing team, with group discussions where perspectives diverged. With a maximum venue capacity of 100, roughly two thirds were recruited through invitation and a third via open call. Generous travel support from the workshop sponsors enabled the participation of early career researchers and attendees from international locations who might otherwise have found travel costs prohibitive.

The final list of participants show a diversity of affiliations and geographies, including many who were participating in an open science conference for the first time. In terms of sectors, it shows a predominance of higher education (30%) followed by community organizations and private funders/non-profit organizations. A significant proportion of attendees' region of origin was North America (62%), followed by European and Latin American participants, with representatives from around the world. More granular information on demographics is available in Annex I.

Program development

A driving force behind the workshop's construction was consideration of how this broad and diverse coalition, animated by the experiences of NASA, CERN, ORCA, and UNESCO, could generate differentiated impact. The concept "Dynamic Convergence" emerged as a way to represent the changing, multiple alignments needed between a diversity of interests and actors to advance the global implementation state of open science.

This notion – that this particular set of individuals and organizations could potentially identify meaningful ways to advance open science– helped define the three themes that guided the workshop's construction:

- **Engagement:** We can bring more people and organizations into open science – as well as extend the reach and impact of open science – by (a) making it more rewarding; (b) making it easier to learn and practice; and/or (c) creating a clearer connection between their priorities/missions and open science (e.g., building trust, engaging communities, accelerating discovery).
- **Coordination:** We can promote collaboration by identifying opportunities to (a) make open science workflows more efficient for both humans and machines; and (b) efficiently share information about promising new activities, evidence-informed success stories, and other key developments in the field of open science

- **Acceleration:** We can speed the transition to an open-by-design research ecosystem by (a) promoting the evidence-based case for how open science directly correlates with research efficiency, inclusivity, public engagement, etc.; and (b) identifying better tools and technologies that make open science demonstrably more efficient and actionable than the status quo.

Within each of these areas, the workshop aimed to create a space that allowed participants to come up with their own ideas and priorities for advancing open science. To that end, a survey was sent out to all participants before the meeting to inform the design of the program. With a roughly 65% response rate, we analyzed this information to identify main topics in which the participants were interested.

This resulted in seven areas organized across the three workshop themes:

Stream	Topic	Key questions
Engagement	Incentives & Recognition	<p>Can we better understand what carrots and sticks have been effective in changing attitudes and behaviors?</p> <p>How do we leverage international efforts like CoARA and DORA to align incentives?</p> <p>Can we rapidly modernize academic incentives to “catch up” with governmental, NGO, and funder advances?</p>
	Coalition Building	<p>How can we garner allies by emphasizing open science’s connection to an inclusive, collaborative, transparent, and socially just research environment?</p> <p>How do we “team up with” public engagement, civic science, team science, etc.?</p>

Stream	Topic	Key questions
Engagement	Training	<p>Where is this work currently housed, and how can it be more deeply embedded in institutional and/or disciplinary training/ continuing education?</p> <p>To what extent can/should we link science communication, community engagement, and open science in training programs?</p>
Coordination	Interoperability	<p>Researchers can struggle with learning new systems, re-entering data across multiple forms, etc. Can we improve workflows by using tools like ORCID, PIDs, and DOIs?</p> <p>Can we coordinate to create open systems and data streams to monitor open science activities?</p>
Coordination	Information Sharing	<p>The depth and breadth of open science-related projects are proliferating. How do we make it easy for newcomers, those on the periphery, etc., to become part of the open science community?</p> <p>How do we make it easier for open science community members to stay abreast of developments in the field?</p>
Acceleration	Measurement, Evaluation, & Learning	<p>What evidence exists to demonstrate that open science policies improve pace of discovery, inclusivity, trust in science, etc.? How can we more easily track policy impact?</p>
Acceleration	User Experience	<p>What can the open science community do to make our tools, resources, outputs, etc., much more inviting and relatable for both producers and consumers of science?</p>

With these high-level (“streams”) and more granular (“topics”) priorities identified by participants, the workshop organizers endeavored to craft a meeting agenda that could start with broad perspectives and trends, then pivot towards concrete initiatives, projects, and specific actions. The meeting was structured to establish shared understanding, while also making ample space for the socialization of diverse interests and experiences.

Practically, this included:

- **Panels:** Each day started with an opening moderated discussion, providing overarching views of open science policies (day one) and successful collaborative practices (day two) to set the tone of the agenda.
- **Lightning talks:** During day one we made space for quick explorations of nine open science initiatives that are generating actionable experiences in engagement, coordination, and acceleration.
- **Breakout sessions:** The most bottom-up portion of the agenda was reserved for facilitated discussions around the identified topics from the survey. An open brainstorm on day one was followed by a discussion of concrete plans and strategies on day two. The agenda included reporting out after each day on the discussions.
- **Hackathon:** At the end of the workshop, participants had the opportunity to suggest concrete collaboration opportunities, attracting contributors and potentially engaging them in future activities.

The practical application of this structure is explored in the two sections immediately following.

WORKSHOP EXECUTION

Logistics

Aware of the fact that not all participants were English-native speakers, we used [Wordly](#), an AI-powered translation and captioning tool, to support accessibility.

Wordly could be used to translate the spoken content into various languages in real time during the workshop, and could be accessed directly on mobile devices.

All protocols, including the [Code of Conduct](#) and [COVID guidelines](#), were in place and communicated before the meeting through the [Welcome Packet](#).

Panels & Lightning Talks

The workshop kicked off with a panel discussion entitled, “Perspectives on Open Science Coordination”. Moderated by ORCA Senior Advisor Julieta Arancio, the session featured perspectives from Chelle Gentemann, Open Science Program Scientist at NASA; Kamran Naim, Head of Open Science at CERN; Nokuthula Mchunu, Deputy Director at the African Open Science Platform hosted by the National Research Foundation, South Africa; and Tiffany Straza, Open Science Consultant in the Section of Science, Technology and Innovation Policy at UNESCO. A recording of this session is available [here](#).

The panelists identified several challenges to achieving an "open by default" research ecosystem, including infrastructure limitations, cultural barriers, and the dominance of the Global North in defining scientific standards. They emphasized the need for a broad geographic coalition that integrates diverse scientific practices and knowledge systems.

The discussion called for a shift away from traditional metrics like journal impact factor toward more inclusive measures of quality and impact. The panelists advocated for sustained efforts to promote open science internationally through policies that support transparency, inclusivity, and collaboration, highlighting its potential to democratize knowledge and create a more equitable scientific community.

Day one also featured lightning talks highlighting nine unique and complementary projects. Copies of these presentations may be found [here](#), and a recording of the session is available [here](#). Each speaker highlighted different aspects of open science, from engaging the public and enhancing reproducibility to ethical practices and community building, reflecting a multifaceted approach to advancing open science globally.

Succinct summaries are as follows:

- Laura Trouille (Zooniverse) - Discussed how Zooniverse, as a platform for citizen science, aligns with open science by enabling public participation in scientific research. She highlighted the expansion of Zooniverse and its impact on making science accessible and engaging for the public.
- Simine Vazire (MetaMelb Lab) - Shared insights from the field of psychology, particularly the challenges and reforms following the replication crisis. She emphasized the importance of clear missions, inclusive practices, and transparency in research.
- Noor Johnson and Roberta Turraq Glenn (ELOKA) - Spoke about their work with indigenous communities in the Arctic, documenting local environmental changes and indigenous knowledge. They discussed the importance of ethical data practices and community engagement in their research.
- Kathleen Fitzpatrick (Michigan State) - Presented on her role in promoting open science through digital platforms that facilitate academic collaboration and public engagement. She emphasized the need for sustainable models to support open science infrastructure.

- Malcolm Macleod (UKRN) - Discussed the UK Reproducibility Network's efforts to improve scientific reproducibility in the UK. He highlighted the need for cultural changes in research practices to enhance transparency and integrity.
- Ting Xu (Chinese Open Science Network) - Talked about the growth of open science practices in China and shared strategies for building local open science communities, emphasizing the importance of practical and visible projects that can engage a broader audience.
- Hong Phuc Dang (Pocket Science) - Introduced the Pocket Science Lab, a project aiming to make science tools more accessible and affordable. She discussed the challenges of developing open hardware and the impact of community-driven development.
- Karthik Ram (Navigation Fund) - Discussed the need to align Open Science with technological advances and break down siloes in scientific infrastructure, balancing innovation with sustainability and calling for a reimagining of systems towards public good initiatives.
- Tony Ross-Hellauer (TU Graz) - Introduced the PathOS project, focused on modeling and measuring the impact of Open Science across academia, society, and the economy.

To begin the second day of the workshop, ORCA's Director of Programs & Strategies Erin McKiernan moderated a "Dynamic Convergence" panel, in which speakers from diverse backgrounds and projects discussed what they have learned about collaborating to sustain and grow the open science ecosystem.

Panelists include Julia Stewart Lowndes, Founding Director of Openscapes; Nabil Ksibi, Africa PID Alliance Project Lead; Esther Plomp, Data Steward at Delft University of Technology; and Almendra Cremaschi, Bioleft Co-Founder. A recording of this session is available [here](#).

The panel explored the diverse implementation of open science across regions, populations, and disciplines, focusing on community engagement, inclusive tools, and the challenge of aligning stakeholders with open science goals. Key themes included the need for sustainable practices, long-term funding, supportive policies, and durable infrastructure. The panelists also called for continued dialogue to integrate open science practices and values into the broader research community, as a means to foster inclusivity, collaboration, and transparency.

Breakouts & Hackathon

A central focus of the workshop was converting ideas and discussions into action. To that end, participants broke into smaller groups to more deeply explore the topics surfaced before (and refined during) the event. Each group was overseen by a dedicated facilitator, and tasked with the same guiding questions:

- Given the composition of participants (spanning geographies, sectors, and disciplines), what is this group effectively positioned to achieve together?
- What opportunities, if successfully executed, can significantly advance open science?
- What are some realistic near-term next steps?
- How can we best start a process that will have life beyond these walls and include other people and organizations?

Each group reported back to the larger workshop audience for further discussion and refinement. By the conclusion of the second day, the breakout groups had identified a number of potential projects, as summarized in the table that follows. Specific actions that the workshop organizers intend to take are detailed in the Key Next Steps section at the beginning of this report.

Stream	Topic	Prospective Workstreams
Engagement	Incentives & Recognition	<p>Continuing to seek concrete ways to adapt credit and reward structures to fully recognize a range of open science activities.</p> <p>Leveraging researchers’ power as reviewers to change journal policies and procedures.</p> <p>Creating better transparency into institutional tenure and promotion policies and finding ways to encourage approaches that incorporate open science.</p>
	Coalition Building	<p>Developing an open science champions program to build bridges across communities and disciplines, including ones that may not see themselves in open science.</p> <p>Identifying practical ways to expand what are considered to be the boundaries of open science and nurture a broad coalition. This encompasses both “set piece” events like an annual convening, as well as mechanisms to encourage ongoing, boundary-spanning engagement.</p>
	Training	<p>Designing personas so that open science training can be more readily adapted to serve a wider array of communities.</p> <p>To what extent can/should we link science communication, community engagement, and open science in training programs?</p>

Stream	Topic	Key questions
Coordination	Interoperability & Information Sharing (merged during the first session)	Localizing existing open science tools and information to reach beyond English/western audiences.
		Establishing an annual convening of open science.
Acceleration	Measurement, Evaluation, & Learning	<p>Developing a typology of impact, with an emphasis on creating more efficient ways for open science practitioners to understand and articulate the qualitative impact of their activities.</p> <p>Designing a usable framework for funders and agencies to evaluate the impact of their open science policies. This is less about policy compliance monitoring and more about seeking to assess whether open science policies are impacting science and society in areas like improving equity, increasing public trust in science, accelerating the pace of discovery, etc., and learning from both failures and successes.</p>
	User Experience	Building a “drag-and-drop my dataset” into an AI tool to determine the best place to deposit data, and suggest other datasets similar to yours. In future, the tool could expand to optimize metadata for deposit into that repository, and/or to run a FAIR check.

After the discussions in breakout sessions, the workshop generated a hackathon space for concrete projects to have dedicated collaboration time. The organizers opened a call for projects before the event, which resulted in nine projects. During the event, the call was open again, and two more projects were added.

After a brief introduction to the hackathon methodology, participants joined the projects of their preference and were introduced to specific tasks and topics that the project leads had designed for contribution. A final report-out and sharing ensured that everyone had the chance to make meaningful connections after the event concluded.

LESSONS LEARNED

At the conclusion of the workshop, participants completed an exit survey to help solidify future workstreams (as articulated in the Key Next Steps section) and to provide candid feedback on the event's execution.

While the workshop's structure and setting were generally viewed positively, several key areas for potential improvement were identified:

- **Breakout Groups Construction.** Several attendees felt that breakout groups were too large, making it difficult for everyone to contribute meaningfully. Additionally, while general topics were shared with participants before the meeting, the relatively condensed breakout session time frames made it somewhat challenging to have thorough, nuanced discussions in some instances.
- **Advance Preparation.** Related to the above, some participants suggested socializing breakout topics in advance or having pre-workshop virtual sessions to help focus discussions and pre-identify shared challenges and opportunities. This could help establish common priorities and maximize the limited time together.
- **Meeting Logistics.** While the venue and meeting mechanics were largely praised, additional space for social breaks and a change of scenery was suggested. The setup for meals was not optimal for participants with accessibility considerations.
- **Inclusivity.** Pronouns should have been uniformly requested prior to the workshop for inclusion on name tags. While the Wordly app was helpful for real-time translations, it did not encompass the language needs of every participant.

- **Speed Networking.** Several respondents recommended a structured “rapid introductions” session or similar icebreaker activities to help participants introduce themselves, especially for newcomers or those with social anxiety.

In addition to the above, the workshop organizers note several observations of our own. The efforts to guarantee a diversity of participants can be strengthened in the future by increasing the proportion of participants that apply via open calls.

In some cases the financial support provided, though generous, was not enough to guarantee participation; in other cases, time was a constraint for participants needing visas and other traveling permits. Additionally, we are aware that inclusivity can be practically bounded by a meeting’s location. In order to ensure that traditionally excluded communities are fully empowered to engage in future convenings, these events should be held in locations beyond the Global North.

ORCA intends to take these insights into consideration when designing future open science convenings, and we encourage our co-organizers, and other organizations to do so as well.

APPENDICES

I - Demographics

The tables and charts below show the data on participants' representation during the event, both in terms of geographical region and sector or affiliation.

REGION	REPRESENTATION (%)
North America	62.20
Europe	13.41
Latin America	12.20
Asia	3.66
Africa	3.66
Oceania	2.44
Middle East	1.22
Caribbean	1.22

SECTOR	REPRESENTATION (%)
Higher Ed	30.12
Community Orgs/Other	26.51
Private Funder	12.05
Non-Profit/Philanthropy	9.64
US Agency	7.23
Government	6.02
Professional Society	4.82
Industry/Private Company	2.41
Citizen Science	1.20

II - Full schedule

Day 1

Time	Session Type	Description	Chair	Speakers
8:15-9:00	Opening	Registration and Breakfast		
9:00-9:15	Remarks	Welcome Overview of meeting agenda & goals	Greg Tananbaum	
9:15-10:30	Panel	Perspectives on Open Science Coordination Efforts	Julieta Arancio	Chelle Gentemann, NASA TOPS Tiffany Straza, UNESCO Nokuthula Mchunu, National Research Foundation, South Africa Kamran Naim, CERN
10:30-11:00	Break	Networking		
11:00-12:30	Lightning Talks	Engagement	Erin McKiernan	Laura Trouille, Zooniverse Simine Vazire, MetaMelb Lab Noor Johnson and Roberta Turraq Glenn, ELOKA
		Coordination		Kathleen Fitzpatrick, Michigan State Malcolm Macleod, UKRN Ting Xu, Chinese Open Science Network Hong Phuc Dang, Pocket Science
		Acceleration		Karthik Ram, Navigation Fund Tony Ross-Hellauer, TU Graz
12:30-1:30	Lunch			

Time	Session Type	Description	Chair	Speakers
1:30-3:00	Breakouts	Engagement	Shannon Dosemagen	Facilitated group discussion
		Coordination	Malvika Sharan	Facilitated group discussion
		Acceleration	Esther Plomp	Facilitated group discussion
3:00-3:30	Break	Networking		
3:30-4:30	Discussion	Breakout Reports	Breakout chairs	Shannon Dosemagen Malvika Sharan Esther Plomp
5:30-7:00	Reception	Drinks and hors d'oeuvres		Gerrard Street Kitchen (Darcy)

Day 2

Time	Session Type	Description	Chair	Speakers
8:15-9:00	Breakfast			
9:00-9:15	Remarks	Recap of Day 1 and Introduction to Day 2	Eunice Mercado-Lara	
9:15-10:30	Panel	Dynamic Convergence	Erin McKiernan	Julia Stewart Lowndes, Openscapes Nabil Ksibi, Africa PID Alliance Esther Plomp, TU Delft Almendra Cremaschi, Bioleft
10:30-11:00	Break	Networking		

Time	Session Type	Description	Chair	Speakers
11:00-12:00	Breakouts	Engagement	Shannon Dosemagen	Facilitated group discussion
		Coordination	Malvika Sharan	Facilitated group discussion
		Acceleration	Esther Plomp	Facilitated group discussion
12:00-1:00	Lunch			
1:00-1:45	Discussion	Breakout Reports	Breakout chairs	Shannon Dosemagen Malvika Sharan Esther Plomp
1:45-2:00	Remarks	Roadmap and Next Steps	Greg Tananbaum	
2:00-4:00	Hackathon			

III - List of participants

Name	Affiliation
Adam Jones	Gordon and Betty Moore Foundation
Alan Ku	National Science Library, Chinese Academy of Sciences
Almendra Cremaschi	Bioleft
Batool Almarzouq	Open Science Community Saudi Arabia
Carly Strasser	Chan Zuckerberg Initiative (CZI)
Carolina Botero	Karisma Foundation (Colombia)
Carrie Rountrey	University of Cincinnati
Catherine Aiken	Center for Security and Emerging Technology, Georgetown University
Chelle Gentemann	NASA
Chris Marcum	Office of the Chief Statistician, US
Damian Pattinson	eLife Sciences Publications Ltd
Daniel Ginsberg	American Anthropological Association
Dawid Potgieter	Independent Consultant
Emmanuel Iarussi	Universidad Torcuato Di Tella & MetaDocencia
Erik Gjesfeld	John Templeton Foundation
Erin McKiernan	Open Research Community Accelerator (ORCA)
Esther Plomp	Delft University of Technology
Eunice Mercado-Lara	Open Research Community Accelerator (ORCA)
Fabiano Couto Corrêa da Silva	Researcher, Department of Information Science, Federal University of Rio Grande do Sul
Fernando Perez	U.C. Berkeley
Francisca Oladipo	Thomas Adewumi University
Greg Tananbaum	Open Research Community Accelerator (ORCA)
Guillermina D'Onofrio	Secretariat of Innovation, Science and Technology of Argentina
Hannah Hope	Wellcome Trust
Hao Ye	Community for Rigor / University of Pennsylvania
Holly Hajare	Office of Science and Technology Policy (OSTP - US)
Hong Phuc Dang	FOSSASIA

Name	Affiliation
Ileana Fenwick	Openscapes
Jamaica Jones	NASA
Jessica Polka	Astera Institute
Juan Pablo Flores	Github
Judith Naidorf	Latin American Forum for Research Assessment
Julia Stewart Lowndes	Openscapes
Juliane Baron	Federation of Associations in Behavior & Brain Sciences (FABBS)
Julieta Arancio	Open Research Community Accelerator (ORCA)
Julio Gaitan	Del Rosario University
Jylana Sheats	Aspen Institute
Kamran Naim	CERN
Karthik Ram	Navigation Fund
Kathleen Fitzpatrick	Michigan State
Katie Bannon	World Bank
Kristin Eldon Whyly	Templeton World Charity Foundation (TWCF)
Larisse Faroni Perez	Inter-American Institute for Global Change Research (IAI)
Laura Trouille	Zooniverse
Lisa Federer	National Library of Medicine (US)
Liz Vu	Alfred P. Sloan Foundation
Malcolm Macleod	UK Reproducibility Network
Maliya Malik	American Geosciences Institute
Malvika Sharan	The Alan Turing Institute Open Life Science (OLS)
Maria Soledad Bravo-Marchant	CINCEL Consortium, Agencia Nacional de Investigación y Desarrollo – Chile
Mario Behling	PSLab
Maryam Zaringhalam	Office of Science and Technology Policy (OSTP - US)
Md Anwarul Islam	University of Dhaka
Michael Dougherty	University of Maryland
Michelle Barker	Research Software Alliance
Miriam Kip	QUEST Center at Berlin Institute of Health-Charite, Germany
Molly Madzellan	Federation of Associations in Behavior & Brain Sciences (FABBS)
Monica Granados	Creative Commons

Name	Affiliation
Nabil Ksibi	Africa PID Alliance
Natalie Ward	Chan Zuckerberg Initiative (CZI)
Nathan Alexander	Howard University
Noam Ross	rOpenSci
Nokuthula Mchunu	National Research Foundation, South Africa
Noor Johnson	Exchange for Local Observations and Knowledge of the Arctic (ELOKA)
Nora Papp	Global Research Initiative on Open Science
Pierre Padilla Huamantico	Universidad Catolica Chile, Libre HUB
Rachel Miles	Virginia Tech
Regina Mae Francia	Belmont Forum
Reshama Shaikh	Data Umbrella
Roberta Turraq Glenn	Alaska Arctic Observatory and Knowledge Hub
Ronnie Kinoshita	Center for Security and Emerging Technology, Georgetown University
Samuel Volchenboum	Data for the Common Good, University of Chicago
Sara Rouhi	AIP Publishing
Shai Silberberg	National Institute of Neurological Disorders and Stroke (NINDS)
Shannon Dosemagen	Open Environmental Data Project
Shelley Stall	American Geophysical Union (AGU)
Simine Vazire	University of Melbourne
Steve Pinchotti	Altum & ORCID Board
Susan Singer	St. Olaf College
Tiffany Straza	UNESCO
Tim Errington	Center for Open Science
Ting Xu	Chinese Open Science Network
Tony Ross-Hellauer	Institute of Interactive Systems and Data Science, TU Graz
Tshiamo Motshegwa	African Open Science Platform
Uta Wehn	Citizen Science Global Partnership
Victoria Tianjing Yan	European Molecular Biology Laboratory
Vincenzo Tozzi	Casa de Cultura Tainã / Rede Mocambos
Xiaoli Chen	DataCite
Yo Yehudi	Open Life Science (OLS)

IV - Recordings and additional materials

The discussions taking place during panels and lightning talks were recorded and are shared in ORCA's YouTube channel as follows:

- Panel “Perspectives on Open Science Coordination”: [Link](#)
- Panel “Dynamic Convergence”: [Link](#)
- Lightning talks: [Link](#)

Additionally, the slides for the lightning talks can be found in Zenodo:
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13935409>

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